

Limiting apparent molar volumes and their temperature derivatives for ammonium sulfate, potassium sulfate and aluminium sulfate in aqueous dimethylformamide

P. S. Nikam^{*a}, A. B. Sawant^a, J. S. Aher^b and R. S. Khairnar^c

^aP. G. Department of Physical Chemistry, M. S. G. College, Malegaon-Camp (Nashik)-423 105, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, K. T. H. M. College, Nashik-422 002, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Arts, Science and Commerce College, Deolali-Camp (Nashik)-422 401, India

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Densities of ammonium sulfate, potassium sulfate and aluminium sulfate have been measured in dimethylformamide (DMF) + water, containing 5, 10, 15 and 20 mass% of DMF, at different concentrations and at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K. From these data apparent molar volumes have been derived and analyzed using Masson equation. The limiting apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}°) and slope (S_{ϕ}^*) are interpreted in terms of solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions, respectively. The V_{ϕ}° values vary with temperature as a power series of temperature. The structure-making/breaking capacities of salts have been inferred from the Hepler's criterion.

Thermodynamic investigations play an important role in understanding type and extent of the patterns of molecular associations that exist in liquid mixtures and their sensitivities to variations in composition, temperature, pressure and chemical nature¹. The partial molar volume of a salt is an important thermodynamic property.

DMF is a very good aprotic protophilic solvent and non-associative in nature. Aqueous mixtures of aliphatic amides are used in many investigations of self-aggregation, peptide properties and solubility of drugs². DMF + water mixtures are also most important owing to the H-bonding between water and DMF³.

In continuation of our earlier findings⁴ we present here the measurement of partial molar volumes of ammonium sulfate, potassium sulfate and aluminium sulfate in DMF + water at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K to obtain better insight into solute-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions.

Results and Discussion

The apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}) was calculated from the density values of the solutions using the relationship,

$$V_{\phi} = 1000(d_0 - d)/(cd_0) + M_2/d_0 \quad (1)$$

where c is the molar concentration of solute, d and d_0 are the densities of solution and solvent respectively, and M_2 is the formula weight of the solute. The correction to V_{ϕ} due to hydrolysis of salts may be negligible, since the strong H-bonding between DMF and water will reduce the hydrolysis of these salts by free water molecules considerably.

Since the data concerning the pressure dependence of the dielectric constant of the DMF + water are not available, the limiting apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}°) was calculated by the Masson empirical equation⁵,

$$V_{\phi} = V_{\phi}^{\circ} + S_{\phi}^* c^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where S_{ϕ}^* is a constant dependent on charge and salt type and can be related to solute-solute interactions and V_{ϕ}° is the limiting apparent molar volumes. These values estimated by computerized least-squares method, correlation coefficient greater than 0.999, along with standard errors are included in Table 1

The experimental S_{ϕ}^* values (Table 1) at different temperatures are positive in DMF + water indicating presence of solute-solute interactions. As expected S_{ϕ}^* value decreases with rise in temperature in 5 and 10 mass% DMF for all the salts, which is attributed to more violent thermal agitation at higher temperature resulting in diminishing force of solute-solute interactions (ionic dissociation)⁶. The increase of S_{ϕ}^* with increase of temperature in 15 and 20 mass% DMF for the salts suggests that more and more solute is accommodated in the void space left in the packing of large associated solvent molecules.

To examine the solute-solvent interactions, the V_{ϕ}° values can be used. Table 1 reveals that V_{ϕ}° values are positive as well as negative. The values in 5 and 10 mass% DMF indicate that solvent molecules are loosely attached to solute which expands with increase of temperature, thus

Table 1. Limiting partial molar volumes (V_{ϕ}°) and experimental slopes (S_v°) of salts in DMF + water at different temperatures

Mass % DMF	$V_{\phi}^{\circ} / (\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1})$				$S_v^{\circ} (\text{cm}^3 \text{dm}^{1/2} \text{mol}^{-3/2})$			
	298.15	303.15	308.15	313.15	298.15	303.15	308.15	313.15 K
Ammonium sulfate								
5	-00.56 (0.34)	19.30 (0.20)	23.69 (0.31)	34.87 (0.21)	194.91 (1.60)	121.93 (0.96)	110.70 (1.46)	75.73 (1.01)
10	8.16 (0.23)	15.08 (0.53)	21.88 (0.16)	24.40 (0.14)	157.18 (1.06)	135.97 (2.51)	112.02 (0.77)	94.98 (0.67)
15	1.50 (0.30)	-18.58 (0.47)	-19.82 (0.27)	-38.42 (0.37)	179.75 (1.39)	250.88 (2.19)	233.48 (1.26)	303.31 (1.72)
20	-8.41 (0.27)	-29.08 (0.35)	-35.02 (0.31)	-47.13 (0.44)	214.62 (1.28)	267.83 (1.63)	287.29 (1.45)	329.77 (2.08)
Potassium sulfate								
5	-00.45 (0.23)	11.01 (1.32)	20.07 (0.12)	21.77 (0.43)	136.44 (1.08)	90.27 (6.22)	65.20 (0.59)	59.38 (2.04)
10	-13.75 (0.25)	-05.73 (0.19)	-00.38 (1.18)	03.82 (0.14)	178.84 (1.18)	151.08 (0.91)	130.85 (5.55)	112.20 (0.67)
15	-16.47 (0.36)	-31.10 (0.15)	-39.28 (0.25)	-57.23 (0.66)	179.29 (1.67)	213.32 (0.71)	242.24 (1.16)	295.22 (3.09)
20	-36.49 (0.40)	-48.06 (0.79)	-54.44 (0.31)	-65.24 (0.38)	251.15 (1.86)	287.64 (3.71)	306.16 (1.47)	333.50 (1.80)
Aluminium sulfate								
5	256.11 (0.29)	263.73 (0.20)	266.46 (0.14)	270.84 (0.20)	175.61 (1.38)	148.25 (0.96)	147.33 (0.64)	139.31 (0.93)
10	247.86 (0.27)	269.25 (0.11)	282.03 (0.19)	284.64 (1.22)	194.58 (1.27)	125.25 (0.50)	90.61 (0.88)	85.18 (5.71)
15	279.71 (0.29)	264.43 (0.24)	258.80 (0.20)	237.75 (0.34)	86.87 (1.36)	123.73 (1.13)	131.79 (0.96)	214.99 (1.60)
20	274.79 (1.60)	253.59 (0.34)	252.60 (0.57)	240.62 (1.83)	99.24 (7.50)	161.98 (1.62)	164.41 (2.66)	208.90 (8.61)

*Values in paranthesis are standard errors.

Table 2. Values of a_i for computerized least-square representation of salts in DMF + water

Mass% DMF	Ammonium sulfate			Potassium sulfate			Aluminium sulfate		
	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_0	a_1	a_2
5	-8763.57	55.27	-0.09	-9564.71	61.17	-0.09	-3048.39	20.74	-0.03
10	-4412.40	27.88	-0.04	-3926.45	24.51	-0.04	-18020.45	117.26	-0.19
15	2103.02	-11.47	0.01	-2357.88	17.81	-0.03	-4324.55	32.64	-0.06
20	8710.73	-54.77	0.08	1234.30	-6.56	0.01	9498.71	-58.43	0.09

resulting in higher values of V_{ϕ}° at higher temperature. In solutions in 15 and 20 mass% DMF solutions, V_{ϕ}° values decrease with increase of temperature for all the salts under investigation, suggesting more electrostrictive solvation at higher temperature. Similar results are reported for some 1 : 1 electrolytes in aqueous DMF⁷.

The variation of V_{ϕ}° with temperature of the salts in solvents follows polynomial equation,

$$V_{\phi}^{\circ} = a_0 + a_1T + a_2T^2 \quad (3)$$

over the temperature range under the investigation. The coefficients a_i 's are presented in Table 2.

The apparent molar expansibilities, calculated from

equation, $\phi_E^{\circ} = [\partial V_{\phi}^{\circ} / \partial T]_p$, for all the salts are included in Table 3. The ϕ_E° values for all the salts in 5 and 10 mass% DMF solutions decrease with increase of temperature, suggesting that these salts behave like common salts¹ in these solvents. However, ϕ_E° values of all the salts in 15 and 20 mass% DMF increase with increase of temperature. The increase in magnitude per degree temperature is positive indicating thereby that the behaviour of all these salts is similar to that of symmetrical quaternary ammonium alkyl salts¹. This can also be ascribed to 'caging effect'⁸.

For determining long-range structure-making and structure-breaking capacities of solute in different solvents, following equation of Hepler⁹ was used,

$$[\partial C_p/\partial p]_T = -[\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2]_p \quad (4)$$

The values of $[\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2]_p$ are summarized in Table 4. According to Hepler, structure-making solute should have positive value and structure-breaking solutes negative value of the term $[\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2]_p$ respectively.

Table 3. ϕ_\pm^E ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-3} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) for the salts in different concentrations of DMF + water at different temperatures

Mass % DMF	298.15	303.15	308.15	313.15 K
Ammonium sulfate				
5	3.52	2.65	1.78	0.91
10	1.77	1.33	0.89	0.45
15	-2.64	-2.49	-2.35	-2.20
20	-3.73	-2.87	-2.01	-1.16
Potassium sulfate				
5	2.98	2.00	1.03	0.05
10	1.73	1.35	0.97	0.59
15	-2.11	-2.44	-2.78	-3.11
20	-1.97	-1.89	-1.81	-1.74
Aluminium sulfate				
5	1.42	1.10	0.78	0.45
10	5.28	3.40	1.52	-0.35
15	-1.77	-2.34	-2.91	-3.50
20	-3.46	-2.53	-1.61	-0.69

Table 4. The term $[\partial^2 V_\phi^0/\partial T^2]_p$ ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-2}$) for salts in DMF + water

Salt	Mass % DMF			
	5	10	15	20
Ammonium sulfate	-0.18	-0.09	0.03	0.17
Potassium sulfate	-0.19	-0.08	-0.07	0.01
Aluminium sulfate	-0.06	-0.38	-0.11	0.18

Two different interaction models are suggested¹⁰ for DMF + water system : (a) complexes of the type DMF.(H₂O)₃ and (b) the DMF + water interaction model leading to extended cluster like structure through H-bonding.

In the water-rich region (5 and 10 mass% DMF), DMF molecules are added interstitially into cavities of water keeping water structure intact. However, with addition of more DMF, the cavities are filled and solvent-solvent interactions become stronger reducing the ability of ions added to promote structure of the solvent¹¹. Therefore, these salts behave as structure-breakers in 5 and 10 mass% DMF. Further addition of DMF to water progressively disrupts the structure of water¹². In the high DMF region, the system exhibits phase separation resulting in clustering of water molecules surrounded by DMF and water molecules near to each other on the surface of the cluster. The new structure of the solvent will solvate added ions mostly by DMF.

This in fact is observed in solutions in 15 and 20 mass% DMF, making the solutes structure-promoters in these solvents.

Experimental

Water was distilled over alkaline KMnO₄, followed by further distillation over H₂SO₄ (electric conductance of distilled water varied between (7 to 9) × 10⁻⁷ Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹). DMF (99.5% pure, sd. fine-chem) was dried by refluxing for 24 h over CaO and then fractionally distilled under reduced pressure; the middle fraction was collected and kept over solid KOH pellets and again distilled under reduced pressure. The purity of DMF was ascertained by comparing densities at different temperatures with the corresponding literature values¹³. Conductivity water and purified DMF were mixed to give 5, 10, 15 and 20 mass% DMF mixtures, which served as solvents.

Ammonium sulfate, potassium sulfate and aluminium sulfate (sd. fine-chem and Ranbaxy, purity >99.5%) were dried over P₂O₅ to constant mass before use. Known masses of the salts (accuracy ±0.01 mg) were dissolved in a particular solvent to give a concentration of 0.1 M; this served as the stock solution. Further concentrations were obtained by using dilution technique. Salt concentrations varied from 0.008 to 0.1 M. The solutions were stored in dark-coloured bottles and kept in a dry box.

Density was measured by using a 16 cm³ double-arm pycnometer as described earlier³. The pycnometer filled with air-bubble-free experimental liquids was kept in a transparent-walled water-bath (±0.01 K) for at least 10–15 min to attain thermal equilibrium. The positions of the liquid levels in the two arms were recorded with the help of a traveling microscope (±0.01 mm). The estimated accuracy of density measurement was ±0.00002 g cm⁻³.

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